

Relationships between geomagnetic Ap-index and parameters of the acupuncture points as well as neuroendocrine-immune complex in patients with its dysfunction

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Background. Back in 1990, YuP Limansky hypothesized acupuncture points (AP) as polymodal receptors of the ecoceptive sensitivity system. In the process of hypothesis development in 2003 an existence of separate functional system of regulation of electromagnetic balance of organism has been substantiated and a working conception of light therapy has been formulated. In line with this hypothesis, we set out to analyze the relationships between the disturbances of the geomagnetic field (Ap-index) and the electrical conductivity of a number of AP, on the one hand, and the parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune complex in patients with its dysfunction, on the other. **Material and methods.** The object of observation were 21 men (24-63 y) and 20 women (30-72 y) with neuroendocrine-immune complex dysfunction. Each patient was tested twice with an interval of 4 days. Retrospectively we recorded the geomagnetic Ap-Index on the day of testing and during the previous 7 days, using resource <https://www.spaceweatherlive.com/>. Recorded the electrical conductivity of 9 pairs of AP, electroencephalogram (EEG) and heart rate variability (HRV) parameters, determined the plasma level of cortisol, triiodothyronine and testosterone, the content of lymphocytes expressing CD3, CD4, CD25, CD8, CD22 and CD56 receptors, the serum level of circulating immune complexes, immunoglobulins classes M, G, A, C-reactive protein, IL-1 β and IL-6. The state of phagocytic function of neutrophils estimated by microbial count and phagocytic and killing indices against Staphylococcus aureus and Escherichia coli. **Results.** During the week, the average level of Ap-index ranged from 7 to 13 nT. Maximum coefficients of multiple correlation with APs parameters were detected for Ap-index on 6 day before ($R=0,552$) and on the day of testing ($R=0,470$), with EEG parameters on the eve of registration ($R=0,708$) and on 6 day before its ($R=0,685$), with immunity parameters on the eve of blood sampling ($R=0,768$) and on 5 day before its ($R=0,758$), with HRV&Hormonal parameters on 2 ($R=0,506$) and 7 ($R=0,403$) days before testing. The canonical correlation between Ap-indices for 7 days before and on the day of testing, and the parameters APs is 0,661; EEG parameters is 0,886; HRV&Hormonal parameters is 0,766 and immunity parameters is 0,921. APs parameter are closely related to the EEG ($R=0,997$) and HRV&Hormonal parameters ($R=0,740$). In turn, the immune parameters are closely related to the EEG ($R=0,944$) and HRV&Hormonal parameters ($R=0,714$). **Conclusion.** Disturbances of the geomagnetic field (Ap-index) causes a significant immediate modulating effect on the parameters of neuroendocrine-immune complex, apparently through acupuncture points as polymodal receptors of the ecoceptive sensitivity system.

Key words: geomagnetic Ap-index, acupuncture points, neuroendocrine-immune complex, relationships, humans.

INTRODUCTION

We dedicate this article to two geniuses who are not recognized for life and even persecuted, but without whom this study would never have occurred to us.

Alexandr L. Chizhevsky, the founder of Heliobiology.
Yuriy P. Limansky, the author of hypothesis about the AP as polymodal receptors of the ecoceptive sensitivity system.

In 1936, the founder of the Heliobiology AL Chizhevsky suggested correlation of some biological processes on the Earth with cycles of Solar activity [1]. Unfortunately, newborn science suffered the same fate as Soviet genetics ...

The geomagnetic field is a fundamental nature of the planet that is produced by the geodynamo of the Earth's outer core. There is evidence that changes in this field can affect biological systems [2Halberg F et al, 2000; 3Zhadin MN, 2001]. While geomagnetic field deflects the solar wind particles, any changes in the density or the velocity of the solar wind interact with the magnetosphere and cause temporary alterations in the field that is measurable at the Earth surface [4Dubrov A, 2013]. This phenomenon is called geomagnetic disturbance or geomagnetic activity. The concept of space-weather is relatively new and the main researches about this phenomenon have been done in recent four decades. Space-weather defined as the conditions in space that affect Earth, consequences of flowing ionized particle of the solar wind against geomagnetic field. However, geomagnetic field acts like a shield and deflect most of the solar charged particles, it is also impressed and altered by solar wind. These geomagnetic field alterations are called geomagnetic disturbances. For quantifying geomagnetic disturbances, several indices such as Planetary K index (Kp) and Planetary A index (Ap) were defined [5Hanslmeier A, 2007].

Back in 1990, YuP Limansky [6] hypothesized acupuncture points as polymodal receptors of the ecoceptive sensitivity system. In the process of hypothesis development in 2003 an existence of separate functional system of regulation of electromagnetic balance of organism has been substantiated and a working conception of light therapy has been formulated [7]. As a basis, there is a possibility to use the acupuncture points for input of biologically necessary electromagnetic waves into the system of their conductors in a body that might be considered as a transport facility for energy of the polarized electromagnetic waves. Zones-recipients are organ shaving an electromagnetic dysbalance due to excess of biologically inadequate radiation and being the targets for peroxide oxidation. Foremost, a body has the neuro-hormonal and immune regulatory systems. Electromagnetic stimulation or modification of functions of the zones-recipients determines the achievement of therapeutic and useful effects, and their combination with local reparative processes allows to attain a clinical goal. Authors show the experimental facts in support of a hypothesis that a living organism can perceive an action of the electromagnetic fields of optical range not only via the visual system, but also through the off-nerve receptors (specific energy-sensitive proteins detecting critical changes of energy in cells and functioning as the “sensory” cell systems), as well as via the acupuncture points.

Recently, on the example of patients with multiple sclerosis and radiculopathy, we found an immediate immunotropic effects of the disturbances of the geomagnetic field by analyzing the relationships between immunity parameters and the Ap-index. The canonical correlation between Ap-indices for 7 days before and on the day of blood collection, on the one hand, and the levels of CD4⁺, CD56⁺, CD25⁺ and CD8⁺ lymphocytes and the concentration of IgM and IL-1 β - on the other hand, was very strong (R=0,741). Thus, disturbances of the geomagnetic field causes a significant immediate modulating effect on the level of immune parameters in the blood, mostly T-helpers (suppressing) and natural killers (enhancing) [8Popovych IL et al, 2021].

The data available in the literature give grounds for assumptions about the **direct** effect of disturbances of the geomagnetic field on immunocytes, and **indirectly**, through immunotropic neurotransmitters and hormones.

Our hypothesis is as follows. Disturbances of the geomagnetic field are perceived by acupuncture points. The information obtained is transmitted to neurons and endocrinocytes, the mediators of which, in turn, affect immunocytes. The purpose of this study is to test this hypothesis.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The object of observation were 21 men (24-63; 44 \pm 12 y) and 20 women (30-72; 49 \pm 12 y) with neuroendocrine-immune complex dysfunction (increased level of HRVs-markers of sympathetic tone and decreased markers of vagal tone, moderate hypocortisolemia, decreased parameters of phagocytosis by neutrophils of gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria, the level of T-helpers, but increased levels of NK- and B-lymphocytes, Igg G and M). Each patient was examined twice with an interval of 4 days. Observations were carried out on 09.06. and 13.06. 2015 (13 men and 3 women), 14.09. and 18.09. 2015 (1 man and 4 women), 27-28.03. and 04-05.04. 2018 (3 men and 7 women), 28.01 and 01.02. 2019 (4 men and 6 women). Retrospectively we recorded the geomagnetic Ap-Index (average value of variations of the Earth's magnetic field as a marker of geomagnetic activity) on the day of testing and during the previous 7 days, using a publicly available information resource <https://www.spaceweatherlive.com/>.

Electrical conductivity recorded in follow acupuncture points: Pg(ND), TR(X), MC(AVL), C(V), LY, Dg(Al), GI, IG, SPE at Right and Left side. Used complex "Medissa". For each pair, the Laterality Index (LI) was calculated according to the formula:

$$LI, \% = [200 \cdot (\text{Right} - \text{Left}) / (\text{Right} + \text{Left})]$$

To assess the parameters of heart rate variability (HRV) we recorded during 7 min electrocardiogram in II lead (software and hardware complex "CardioLab+HRV", KhAI-MEDICA, Kharkiv). For further analysis the following parameters HRV were selected. Temporal parameters (Time Domain Methods): the standard deviation of all NN intervals (SDNN), the square root of the mean of the sum of the squares of differences between adjacent NN intervals (RMSSD), the percent of interval differences of successive NN intervals greater than 50 msec (pNN₅₀); Triangular Index (TNN). Spectral parameters (Frequency Domain Methods): power spectral density (PSD) bands of HRV - high-frequency (HF, range 0,4 \div 0,15 Hz), low-frequency (LF, range 0,15 \div 0,04 Hz), very low-frequency (VLF, range 0,04 \div 0,015 Hz) and ultralow-frequency (ULF, range 0,015 \div 0,003 Hz). Calculated classical indexes: LF/HF, LFnu=100%•LF/(LF+HF) [9,10]. Baevsky's parameters. Heart rate (HR), Mode (Mo), the Amplitude of Mode (AMo), Variational Sweep (MxDMn), Vegetative Balance Index (VBI=AMo/MxDMn), Stress Index (BSI=AMo/2•Mo•MxDMn) as well as Baevsky's Activity of Regulatory Systems Index (BARS) [11].

Simultaneously EEG recorded a hardware-software complex “NeuroCom Standard” (KhAI MEDICA, Kharkiv) monopolar in 16 loci (Fp1, Fp2, F3, F4, F7, F8, C3, C4, T3, T4, P3, P4, T5, T6, O1, O2) by 10-20 international system, with the reference electrodes A and Ref tassels on the ears. Among the options considered the average EEG amplitude (μV), average frequency (Hz), frequency deviation (Hz), index (%), coefficient of asymmetry (%) and absolute ($\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$) and relative (%) PSD of basic rhythms: β ($35\div 13$ Hz), α ($13\div 8$ Hz), θ ($8\div 4$ Hz) and δ ($4\div 0,5$ Hz) in all loci, according to the instructions of the device. In addition, calculated Laterality Index (LI) for PSD each Rhythm using formula:

$$\text{LI, \%} = \Sigma [200 \cdot (\text{Right} - \text{Left}) / (\text{Right} + \text{Left})] / 8$$

We calculated also for each locus CE Shannon’s Entropy (h) of normalized PSD using formula [12,13]:

$$h = - [\text{PSD}\alpha \cdot \log_2 \text{PSD}\alpha + \text{PSD}\beta \cdot \log_2 \text{PSD}\beta + \text{PSD}\theta \cdot \log_2 \text{PSD}\theta + \text{PSD}\delta \cdot \log_2 \text{PSD}\delta] / \log_2 4$$

Among hormones we determined major adaptation hormones Cortisol, Testosterone and Triiodothyronine (by the ELISA with the use of analyzer “RT-2100C” and corresponding sets of reagents from “Алкор Био”, XEMA Co., Ltd and DRG International Inc.).

Immune status evaluated as described in the manuals [14]. For phenotyping subpopulations of lymphocytes used the methods of rosette formation with sheep erythrocytes on which adsorbed monoclonal antibodies against receptors CD3, CD4, CD25, CD8, CD22 and CD56 from company “Granum” (Kharkiv) with visualization under light microscope with immersion system. Subpopulation of T cells with receptors high affinity (T-active) determined by test of “active” rosette formation. The state of humoral immunity judged by the concentration in serum of Circulating Immune Complexes (by polyethylene glycol precipitation method) and Immunoglobulins classes M, G, A (ELISA, analyzer “Immunochem”, USA). In addition, the level of C-reactive Protein, IL-1 β and IL-6 was determined (by the ELISA with the use of analyzer “RT-2100C” and corresponding set of reagents from “Vector-Best”, RF).

Parameters of phagocytic function of neutrophils estimated as described by SD Douglas and PG Quie [15] with moderately modification by MM Kovbasnyuk [16,17]. The objects of phagocytosis served daily cultures of Staphylococcus aureus (ATCC N 25423 F49) as typical specimen for Gram-positive Bacteria and Escherichia coli (O55 K59) as typical representative of Gram-negative Bacteria. Both cultures obtained from Laboratory of Hydro-Geological Regime-Operational Station JSC “Truskavets’kurort”. Take into account the following parameters of Phagocytosis: activity (percentage of neutrophils, in which found microbes - Hamburger’s Phagocytic Index PhI), intensity (number of microbes absorbed one phagocytes - Microbial Count MC or Right’s Index) and completeness (percentage of dead microbes - Killing Index KI). On the basis of the recorded partial parameters of Phagocytosis, taking into account the Neutrophils (N) content of 1 L blood, we calculated the integral parameter - Bactericidal Capacity of Neutrophils (BCCN) by the formula [18,19]:

$$\text{BCCN} (10^9 \text{ Bacteria/L}) = N (10^9/\text{L}) \cdot \text{PhI} (\%) \cdot \text{MC} (\text{Bact/Phag}) \cdot \text{KI} (\%) \cdot 10^{-4}$$

We calculated also the Entropy (h) of Immunocytogram (ICG) and Leukocytogram (LCG) using formulas [20]:

$$h_{\text{ICG}} = - [\text{CD4} \cdot \log_2 \text{CD4} + \text{CD8} \cdot \log_2 \text{CD8} + \text{CD22} \cdot \log_2 \text{CD22} + \text{CD56} \cdot \log_2 \text{CD56}] / \log_2 4$$

$$h_{\text{LCG}} = - [L \cdot \log_2 L + M \cdot \log_2 M + E \cdot \log_2 E + \text{PMNN} \cdot \log_2 \text{PMNN} + \text{RSN} \cdot \log_2 \text{RSN}] / \log_2 5$$

Results processed by using the software package “Statistica 64”.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the week before testing, the average level of Ap-index was in the range of $7\div 13$ nT (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Values of Ap-Index (M±SE) on the day of testing and during the previous 7 days

Screenings of correlations between Ap-indices and AP performed (Table 1).

Table 1. Matrix of correlations between Ap-Indices and AP conductivity

AP	Ap-7	Ap-6	Ap-5	Ap-4	Ap-3	Ap-2	Ap-1	Ap0
IG L	0,15	0,40	-0,10	-0,01	-0,01	0,04	0,05	0,15
Dg(AI) R	0,12	0,15	-0,06	-0,03	-0,08	-0,09	-0,02	0,13
GI L	0,08	0,10	-0,03	0,00	0,06	-0,16	-0,01	0,01
LY LI	0,04	0,21	-0,12	0,09	0,06	0,04	0,06	0,09
Dg(AI) LI	0,04	0,11	-0,08	0,00	-0,04	-0,03	0,05	0,08
IG LI	-0,13	-0,36	-0,08	0,05	0,10	-0,04	-0,06	-0,10
GI LI	-0,04	-0,23	0,11	0,09	0,01	-0,07	-0,01	-0,12
GI R	-0,02	-0,26	0,09	0,13	0,04	-0,16	-0,02	-0,16
LY L	-0,01	-0,20	0,12	0,11	0,05	0,13	0,00	-0,11
SPE L	-0,10	-0,13	0,09	0,19	0,18	-0,01	-0,13	-0,32
TR(X) L	-0,08	-0,14	0,04	-0,07	0,00	0,09	0,15	0,00
MC(AVL) LI	-0,09	-0,22	-0,16	-0,23	-0,22	-0,05	0,34	0,15
IG R	-0,02	-0,12	-0,01	-0,16	-0,11	0,07	0,24	0,15
Pg(ND) LI	0,08	-0,02	0,02	-0,04	-0,02	0,04	0,19	0,14
C(V) R	-0,03	0,01	0,08	-0,06	-0,09	0,06	0,06	0,13
C(V) L	-0,07	-0,05	-0,03	-0,05	-0,02	-0,05	0,00	-0,01
C(V) LI	0,06	0,05	0,05	0,01	-0,02	0,05	0,01	0,05
LY R	0,05	0,04	0,07	0,16	0,08	0,14	0,07	0,10
Dg(AI) L	-0,06	-0,09	-0,02	-0,02	-0,02	0,02	-0,02	-0,05
SPE R	0,01	-0,00	-0,05	0,14	-0,06	0,05	-0,10	0,05
SPE LI	0,07	0,14	-0,04	-0,13	-0,16	0,08	0,07	0,23
Pg(ND) R	-0,05	-0,06	0,06	0,08	0,18	0,16	-0,01	-0,16
Pg(ND) L	-0,08	-0,05	0,06	0,10	0,19	0,14	-0,09	-0,22
MC(AVL) R	-0,08	-0,14	-0,06	-0,08	-0,02	0,09	0,23	0,02
MC(AVL) L	-0,05	-0,06	0,01	0,02	0,08	0,12	0,09	-0,05
TR(X) R	-0,06	-0,14	0,02	-0,12	-0,03	0,08	0,17	0,04
TR(X) LI	0,05	0,01	-0,07	-0,12	-0,09	-0,04	0,04	0,11

Note. According to calculations by the formula: $|r| = \frac{\exp[2t/(n-1,5)^{0,5}] - 1}{\exp[2t/(n-1,5)^{0,5}] + 1}$ for a sample of n=82 critical value |r| at p<0,05 (t>2,00) is 0,22, at p<0,01 (t>2,66) is 0,29, at p<0,001 (t>3,46) is 0,37.

Construction of regression models by stepwise exclusion to reach the maximum value of Adjusted R^2 found that the electrical conductivity of APs and its symmetry is most closely correlated with Ap-index 6 days before registration (Table 2 and Fig. 7).

Table 2. Regression Summary for Ap-6

$R=0,552$; $R^2=0,305$; Adjusted $R^2=0,259$; $F_{(5,8)}=6,7$; $p<10^{-4}$

		Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	$t_{(76)}$	p-level
Variables	r		Intercept	-42,4	37,8	-1,12	0,266
IG Left, units	0,40	-0,244	0,105	-0,520	0,224	-2,32	0,023
IG LI, %	-0,36	1,621	0,554	1,571	0,537	2,93	0,005
GI Right, units	-0,26	0,481	0,108	0,00009	0,00002	4,44	10^{-4}
MC(AVL) LI, %	-0,22	1,331	0,555	0,703	0,293	2,40	0,019
TR(X) Right, units	-0,14	-0,234	0,099	-58,81	24,91	-2,36	0,021

According to the analysis of the canonical correlation between Ap-indices and AP-conductivity, it was found (Table 3) that the geomagnetic root receives the maximum factor load from the Ap-Index 6 days before testing. Much less, but unidirectional load on the root gives Ap-Index 4 and 3 days before the registration of conductivity. Instead, the Ap-Index on the eve of the measurement gives the load with the opposite sign. Ap-indices on other days give meager factor loads and were not included by the program in the model.

The effective root is represented, on the one hand, by APs whose electrical conductivity **increases** under the influence of the Ap-index 6 days before registration or its lateralization shifts to the **right**, and on the other hand, APs whose symmetry shifts to the **left** or whose electrical conductivity **decreases**. The third constellation is represented by three parameters that are **upregulated** by Ap-1 instead **downregulated** by Ap-indices on other days.

In general, the electrical conductivity of these APs or its symmetry is determined by Ap-indices by 44% (Fig. 2).

Table 3. Factor Structure Matrix for Canonical Roots of Ap-Indices and AP conductivity

Left set	R
Ap-6, nT	-0,765
Ap-4, nT	-0,308
Ap-3, nT	-0,144
Ap-1, nT	0,494
Right set	R
IG left	-0,527
Dg(Al) right	-0,234
GI left	-0,153
LY LI	-0,305
Dg(Al) LI	-0,179
IG LI	0,480
GI LI	0,256
LY left	0,260
GI right	0,240
SPE left	0,169
TR(X) left	0,306
MC(AVL) LI	0,422
Pg(ND) LI	0,214
IG right	0,293

$R=0,661$; $R^2=0,437$; $\chi^2_{(84)}=108$; $p=0,038$; $\Lambda \text{ Prime}=0,215$

Fig. 2. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between Ap Geomagnetic indices during 6 days before testing (X-line) and electrical conductivity of Acupuncture Points (Y-line)

Table 4. Factor Structure Matrix for first pair APs/EEG Canonical Roots

Left set	R1
IG right	-0,995
LY left	-0,780
LY LI	0,558
Dg(Al) LI	0,335
TR(X) left	0,195
Right set	R1
PSD P3-0, %	-0,932
PSD C3-0, %	-0,754
PSD C4-0, %	-0,653
PSD T6-0, %	-0,641
PSD F7-0, %	-0,618
PSD F4-0, %	-0,610
PSD T5-0, %	-0,575
PSD F3-0, %	-0,546
PSD P4-0, %	0,788
PSD P4-0, $\mu V^2/Hz$	0,618
PSD O1-0, %	0,749
PSD O1-0, $\mu V^2/Hz$	0,626
PSD O2-0, %	0,724
PSD O2- α , %	-0,719
PSD P4- α , %	-0,586
PSD T6- α , %	-0,572
PSD O1- α , %	-0,554
PSD F4- α , %	-0,509
PSD C4- α , %	-0,506
Index α , %	-0,482

PSD Fp2- α , %	-0,470
PSD F3- α , %	-0,465
PSD P3- α , %	-0,464
PSD C3- α , %	-0,438
PSD T5- α , %	-0,327
PSD O2- α , $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$	-0,322
Amplitude α , μV	-0,245
PSD T3- β , $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$	0,332
PSD O2- β , %	0,317
PSD P4- β , %	0,239

$R=0,997$; $R^2=0,994$; $\chi^2_{(280)}=944$; $p<10^{-6}$; $\Lambda \text{ Prime}<10^{-6}$

Fig. 3. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between Acupuncture Points (X-line) and EEGs (Y-line) parameters. First pair of Roots

Table 5. Factor Structure Matrix for second pair APs/EEG Canonical Roots

Left set	R2
LY left	0,506
LY LI	-0,497
Dg(AI) LI	-0,312
TR(X) left	-0,203
Right set	R2
PSD T5- α , $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$	0,524
PSD T5- α , %	0,520
PSD P3- α , $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$	0,523
PSD P3- α , %	0,492
Index α , %	0,506
Amplitude α , μV	0,478
PSD O1- α , $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$	0,482
PSD O1- α , %	0,452
PSD P4- α , $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$	0,472
PSD P4- α , %	0,406
PSD O2- α , $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$	0,414
PSD O2- α , %	0,343

PSD T6- α , %	0,375
PSD C3- α , %	0,356
PSD F4- α , %	0,338
PSD C4- α , %	0,335
PSD P4- θ , $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$	0,335
PSD Fp2- α , %	0,329
PSD F3- α , %	0,316
PSD T3- β , $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$	-0,589
PSD P4- β , %	-0,484
PSD O2- β , %	-0,340
Laterality β , %	0,367
Entropy PSD P3	-0,324

$R=0,978$; $R^2=0,956$; $\chi^2_{(238)}=645$; $p<10^{-6}$; $\Lambda \text{ Prime}<10^{-5}$

Fig. 4. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between Acupuncture Points (X-line) and EEGs (Y-line) parameters. Second pair of Roots

Table 6. Matrix of correlations between selected APs conductivity and HRV/Hormonal variables

Variables	Dg(AI) r	Dg(AI) LI	LY LI	GI l	GI r	GI LI	LY l	IG r	TR(X) l
HF PS, msec ²	-0,31	-0,10	-0,13	-0,17	0,27	0,27	0,17	0,29	-0,16
LF PS, msec ²	-0,28	-0,11	-0,19	-0,12	0,24	0,23	0,23	0,28	-0,02
Total Power, msec ²	-0,21	-0,20	-0,12	-0,09	0,16	0,16	0,17	0,18	-0,03
SDNN, msec	-0,21	-0,18	-0,18	-0,09	0,22	0,20	0,22	0,23	-0,08
VLF PS, msec ²	-0,15	-0,22	-0,08	-0,09	0,09	0,11	0,11	0,12	-0,02
Triangular Index, units	-0,14	-0,05	-0,22	-0,08	0,25	0,22	0,23	0,19	-0,05
pNN50, %	-0,15	-0,07	-0,15	-0,18	0,29	0,29	0,17	0,24	-0,18
RMSSD, msec	-0,14	-0,10	-0,16	-0,18	0,30	0,30	0,20	0,30	-0,20
HF/TP, %	-0,09	-0,16	-0,01	-0,14	0,14	0,17	0,07	0,29	-0,19

Heart Rate, beats/min	0,03	-0,02	0,21	0,09	-0,23	-0,21	-0,11	0,01	0,10
Baevsky's Stress Ind, ln	0,11	0,01	0,20	0,06	-0,23	-0,19	-0,19	-0,18	0,07
Amplitude of Mode, %	0,11	0,02	0,20	0,10	-0,22	-0,20	-0,21	-0,21	0,10
LF/(LF+HF), %	0,07	0,07	0,04	0,15	-0,19	-0,21	-0,03	-0,22	0,20
ULF/TP, %	0,06	0,05	-0,01	0,25	-0,00	-0,11	0,01	-0,22	0,08
Testosterone, nM/L	-0,27	-0,08	-0,10	-0,16	0,33	0,31	0,12	-0,13	0,04
Triiodothyronine, nM/L	-0,26	-0,06	-0,02	0,07	0,15	0,08	0,01	-0,16	0,22
Cortisol, nM/L	0,14	0,07	0,25	0,13	-0,15	-0,17	-0,18	-0,24	0,11
Testosterone standard, Z	0,12	0,07	0,19	0,03	-0,16	-0,13	-0,18	-0,17	-0,12

Table 7. Factor Structure Matrix for APs/HRV&Hormonal Canonical Roots

Left set	R
Dg(Al) right	-0,850
LY LI	-0,198
Dg(Al) LI	-0,190
GI left	-0,158
GI right	0,508
GI LI	0,443
LY left	0,218
IG right	0,100
TR(X) left	0,306
Right set	R
Testosterone actual, nM/L	0,517
Triiodothyronine, nM/L	0,515
HF PS, msec ²	0,283
LF PS, msec ²	0,272
Total Power Spectral, msec ²	0,193
SDNN, msec	0,167
VLF PS, msec ²	0,129
Triangular Index, units	0,122
pNN50, %	0,109
RMSSD, msec	0,058
Testosterone standardized, Z	-0,104
Heart Rate, beats/min	-0,089
Baevsky's Stress Index, ln	-0,088
Cortisol, nM/L	-0,029

R=0,740; R²=0,548; $\chi^2_{(126)}=156$; p=0,035; Λ Prime=0,104

Fig. 5. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between Acupuncture Points (X-line) and HRV&Hormonal (Y-line) parameters

Table 8. Regression Summary for Ap-1 Index

R=0,708; R²=0,502; Adjusted R²=0,379; F₍₁₇₎=4,1; p<10⁻⁴

		Beta	St. Err. of Beta	B	St. Err. of B	t ₍₆₅₎	p-level
Variables	r		Intercept	4,51	7,92	0,57	0,571
PSD C4- θ , %	-0,30	-0,357	0,203	-1,032	0,585	-1,76	0,083
PSD F7- θ , %	-0,30	-0,265	0,183	-0,641	0,443	-1,44	0,153
PSD F4- θ , $\mu V^2/Hz$	-0,27	-0,276	0,156	-0,107	0,060	-1,77	0,081
PSD Fp1- θ , %	-0,26	-0,309	0,142	-0,732	0,337	-2,17	0,034
PSD T4- θ , %	-0,26	-0,249	0,147	-12,74	7,55	-1,69	0,096
PSD F4- θ , %	-0,24	0,384	0,191	0,914	0,454	2,01	0,049
PSD P3- θ , %	-0,24	-0,398	0,160	-0,973	0,390	-2,50	0,015
PSD P3- θ , $\mu V^2/Hz$	-0,21	-0,368	0,222	-0,110	0,067	-1,65	0,103
PSD F8- θ , $\mu V^2/Hz$	-0,21	-0,137	0,111	-0,031	0,025	-1,24	0,221
PSD P4- θ , $\mu V^2/Hz$	-0,20	0,647	0,235	0,153	0,056	2,75	0,008
PSD T3- θ , %	-0,20	0,266	0,145	0,838	0,457	1,83	0,071
PSD O1- θ , %	-0,20	0,292	0,166	0,695	0,394	1,76	0,082
Deviation θ , Hz	0,20	0,384	0,102	7,520	2,001	3,76	10 ⁻³
PSD T5- δ , %	0,20	0,297	0,141	0,152	0,072	2,11	0,039
PSD C3- β , %	0,24	0,456	0,112	0,500	0,123	4,07	10 ⁻⁴

Слід відзначити, що поза моделлю виявились відносні PSD T6- θ (r=-0,29), C3- θ (r=-0,28) and F3- θ (r=-0,27), мабуть, через надлишкову або дублюючу інформацію.

Table 9. Factor Structure Matrix for Canonical Roots of Ap-Indices and EEGs parameters

Left set	R
Ap-5, nT	-0,667
Ap-4, nT	-0,293
Ap-3, nT	-0,022
Ap-7, nT	0,264
Ap-6, nT	0,144
Ap-2, nT	-0,252
Ap-0, nT	-0,095
Ap-1, nT	-0,068
Right set	R
PSD T6- δ , $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$	-0,288
PSD F8- δ , $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$	-0,263
PSD Fp1- δ , $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$	-0,218
Amplitude β , μV	0,249
PSD O2- β , $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$	0,240
PSD F3- β , $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$	0,361
PSD F3- β , %	0,206
PSD C3- β , %	0,162
Entropy PSD O2	0,351
PSD T5- θ , %	0,321
PSD O2- θ , %	0,316
PSD F7- δ , %	-0,121
PSD F7- θ , %	0,510
PSD F8- θ , %	0,440
PSD C4- θ , $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$	0,431
PSD C4- θ , %	0,228
PSD Fp1- θ , %	0,342
PSD F4- θ , $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$	0,337
PSD F4- θ , %	0,176
PSD P4- θ , $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$	0,320
PSD T6- θ , %	0,223
PSD C3- θ , %	0,132
PSD T4- θ , %	0,130
PSD T6- α , $\mu\text{V}^2/\text{Hz}$	0,235

$R=0,886$; $R^2=0,786$; $\chi^2_{(280)}=347$; $p=0,004$; $\Lambda \text{ Prime}=0,0028$

Fig. 6. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between Ap Geomagnetic indices before 7 days and on day testing (X-line) and EEG parameters (Y-line)

Table 10. Matrix of correlations between Ap-Indices and HRV&Endocrine parameters

HRV/Hormones	Ap-7	Ap-6	Ap-5	Ap-4	Ap-3	Ap-2	Ap-1	Ap0	Z±SE
Baevsky's ARSI	0,15	-0,04	0,21	0,03	0,17	0,15	0,03	0,02	3,31±0,28
Vegetative Balance Ind	0,36	0,16	-0,00	-0,02	0,13	-0,04	-0,03	0,08	2,30±0,48
Mode	-0,10	-0,03	-0,21	-0,08	-0,12	-0,07	0,11	0,01	-1,21±0,14
AMo	0,32	0,22	-0,05	-0,02	0,12	-0,12	-0,07	0,05	0,38±0,13
MxDMn	-0,23	-0,19	-0,10	-0,06	-0,19	0,10	0,17	0,05	-0,35±0,12
Triangular Index	-0,23	-0,21	-0,08	-0,04	-0,16	0,15	0,16	0,04	0,03±0,19
SDNN	-0,19	-0,17	-0,04	-0,01	0,03	0,20	0,08	-0,09	-0,30±0,09
LF	-0,19	-0,20	-0,03	0,02	-0,01	0,22	0,14	-0,08	0,91±0,30
HF	-0,10	-0,14	-0,17	-0,05	-0,13	0,08	0,11	0,01	-0,36±0,17
LF/HF	-0,10	-0,10	0,24	0,01	0,06	0,06	0,10	0,02	1,71±0,30
LF/(LF+HF)	-0,10	-0,05	0,27	0,12	0,20	0,17	0,08	-0,07	1,22±0,10
VLF	-0,07	-0,05	-0,00	-0,02	0,16	0,13	-0,01	-0,14	-0,13±0,44
ULF	-0,08	-0,10	-0,03	0,10	0,05	0,36	0,01	-0,08	1,56±0,69
ULF/TP	-0,10	-0,08	-0,01	0,07	-0,01	0,19	-0,05	-0,10	0,55±0,24
Cortisol	0,09	0,15	0,01	0,11	0,15	0,00	-0,24	-0,13	-1,04±0,04
									-1,12±0,06
									-0,95±0,06
Triiodothyronine	-0,09	-0,15	-0,11	-0,05	0,02	0,03	-0,15	-0,27	-0,34±0,20
									-0,50±0,27
									-0,16±0,29
Testosterone actual	-0,13	-0,15	0,07	0,05	-0,13	-0,12	-0,02	0,01	
Testosterone standard	0,14	0,09	0,07	0,07	-0,01	-0,30	-0,13	0,04	-0,15±0,20
									1,43±0,44

Для гормонів приведені Z-scores в цілому, а також окремо для чоловіків і жінок.

Table 11. Factor Structure Matrix for Canonical Roots of Ap-Indices and HRV&Endocrine parameters

Left set	R
Ap-2, nT	0,641
Ap-5, nT	0,203
Ap-3, nT	0,165
Ap-4, nT	0,093
Ap-7, nT	-0,151
Ap-6, nT	-0,025
Ap-0, nT	-0,104
Ap-1, nT	0,035
Right set	R
Testosterone, Z-score	-0,789
Testosterone, nM/L	-0,330
Mode, msec	-0,090
ULF, msec ²	0,429
ULF/TP, %	0,311
SDNN, msec	0,258
VLF, msec ²	0,257

Baevsky's ARSI, units	0,197
LF/(LF+HF), %	0,161
AMo, %	-0,146
Vegetative Balance Ind, un	-0,076
Triangular Index, units	0,139
MxDMn, msec	0,089
Triiodothyronine, nM/L	0,336
Cortisol, nM/L	0,002

$R=0,766$; $R^2=0,589$; $\chi^2_{(120)}=194$; $p<10^{-4}$; Λ Prime=0,060

Fig. 7. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between Ap Geomagnetic indices before 7 days and on day testing (X-line) and HRV&Hormonal parameters (Y-line)

Maximum coefficients of multiple correlation with immunity parameters were detected for Ap-index on the eve of blood sampling ($R=0,768$) and 5 days before it ($R=0,758$) while the minimum on 3 ($R=0,541$) and 2 ($R=0,479$) days before sampling.

Table 12. Matrix of correlations between Ap-Indices and Immunity parameters

HRV/Hormones	Ap-7	Ap-6	Ap-5	Ap-4	Ap-3	Ap-2	Ap-1	Ap0	Z±SE
CD4 ⁺ CD25 ⁺ T-regulatory, %	0,10	0,24	0,27	0,06	0,09	-0,00	-0,08	0,15	0,73±0,15
Interleukin-6, ng/L	0,02	0,05	-0,14	-0,13	-0,03	-0,23	0,08	0,04	0,90±0,09
C-Reactive Protein, mg/L	0,02	0,04	-0,16	-0,13	-0,04	-0,27	0,06	0,03	0,64±0,11
Interleukin-1, ng/L	-0,07	-0,16	-0,12	-0,08	-0,09	-0,03	0,14	-0,03	0,59±0,20
CD3 ⁺ CD4 ⁺ T-helper, %	-0,14	-0,26	-0,19	0,03	-0,05	0,01	-0,15	-0,27	-2,23±0,18
CD3 ⁺ CD8 ⁺ T-cytolytic, %	0,00	0,07	0,13	0,09	0,06	0,00	-0,21	-0,05	-0,77±0,20
CD3 ⁺ T-active, %	-0,04	-0,23	-0,22	-0,10	-0,19	-0,09	0,04	-0,06	-0,07±0,10
CD22 ⁺ B-Lymphocytes, %	-0,08	-0,17	-0,02	0,03	-0,06	-0,11	-0,20	-0,19	0,66±0,19
CD56 ⁺ NK-Lymphocytes, %	0,07	0,07	-0,01	-0,09	-0,02	-0,01	0,23	0,17	1,34±0,24
0-Lymphocytes, %	0,12	0,21	0,05	-0,06	0,06	0,09	0,26	0,26	0,63±0,14
Entropy Immunocytogram	-0,03	-0,04	-0,18	-0,07	-0,11	-0,15	-0,12	-0,08	-0,09±0,07
Circulat Immune Compl, un	-0,02	0,02	0,19	0,13	0,07	-0,01	-0,21	-0,08	-0,51±0,11
Immunoglobulins G, g/L	0,07	0,02	0,07	0,07	0,09	-0,03	-0,14	-0,07	1,71±0,15
Immunoglobulins A, g/L	-0,19	-0,30	-0,26	-0,01	-0,11	-0,20	-0,28	-0,40	-0,08±0,21
Immunoglobulins M, g/L	0,12	0,24	-0,14	0,16	0,09	-0,01	-0,24	-0,09	0,79±0,16
Phagocyt Ind vs St. aur., %	0,25	0,31	-0,31	-0,16	-0,06	-0,05	0,25	0,30	0,54±0,04
Microb Count St. aur., B/Ph	0,48	0,41	0,09	0,25	0,31	0,08	-0,35	-0,01	-0,21±0,10
Killing Index vs St. aur., %	0,16	-0,08	0,43	0,42	0,36	0,17	-0,55	-0,39	-1,84±0,13
BCC vs St. aur., 10 ⁹ Bac/L	0,24	0,21	0,28	0,33	0,35	0,02	-0,48	-0,21	-1,45±0,34
Phagocyt Ind vs E.coli, %	-0,04	0,07	-0,28	-0,03	-0,10	-0,21	-0,20	-0,12	1,03±0,06

Microb Count E. coli, B/Ph	0,30	-0,14	-0,11	0,20	0,21	0,02	-0,44	-0,41	0,71±0,12
Killing Index vs E. coli, %	0,37	0,21	0,49	0,43	0,42	0,14	-0,51	-0,18	-2,54±0,09
BCC vs E. coli, 10 ⁹ Bac/L	0,28	0,14	0,17	0,29	0,32	-0,05	-0,51	-0,27	-1,79±0,33
Leukocytes in total, 10 ⁹ /L	-0,06	0,19	0,04	-0,02	0,04	-0,15	-0,04	0,07	1,20±0,26
Eosinophils, %	-0,08	0,17	0,24	0,17	0,09	0,06	-0,05	0,08	-0,21±0,22
Rod-shaped Neutrophils, %	0,02	0,08	0,20	0,18	0,14	0,12	0,00	0,02	-2,39±0,21
PMN Neutrophils, %	-0,01	0,03	-0,16	0,00	-0,04	-0,12	-0,15	-0,09	0,78±0,12
Lymphocytes in total, %	0,08	-0,06	0,14	-0,00	0,13	0,23	0,17	0,02	-0,41±0,11
Monocytes, %	-0,13	-0,11	-0,06	-0,12	-0,22	-0,22	-0,01	0,05	-0,58±0,52

Table 13. Factor Structure Matrix for first Ap/Immune pair of Canonical Roots

Left set	Root 1
Ap-1, nT	0,726
Ap-0, nT	0,481
Ap-7, nT	-0,489
Ap-4, nT	-0,332
Ap-3, nT	-0,290
Right set	Root 1
Microbial Count for E. coli, Bacteria/Phagocyte	-0,723
Bactericidal Capacity vs E. coli, 10 ⁹ Bac/L	-0,557
Immunoglobulins A, g/L	-0,459
Killing Index vs Staph. aureus, %	-0,444
Microbial Count for Staph. aureus, Bacter/Phag	-0,438
Bactericidal Capacity vs Staph. aureus, 10 ⁹ Bac/L	-0,433
Killing Index vs E. coli, %	-0,374
Phagocytosis Index vs E. coli, %	-0,344
Immunoglobulins M, g/L	-0,342
CD3 ⁺ CD4 ⁺ T-helper Lymphocytes	-0,302
Entropy of Immunocytogram	-0,244
CD22 ⁺ B-Lymphocytes, %	-0,241
CD3 ⁺ T-active Lymphocytes, %	-0,121
Circulating Immune Complex, units	-0,110
0-Lymphocytes, %	0,322

Taken together, the variations of the magnetic field in these periods before blood collection determine this constellation of immune parameters by 85% (Fig. 3).

$R=0,921$; $R^2=0,849$; $\chi^2_{(200)}=375$; $p<10^{-6}$; Λ Prime=0,0028

Fig. 8. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between Ap Geomagnetic indices before 7 days and on day blood sampling (X-line) and Immune parameters (Y-line). First pair of Roots

The geomagnetic root of the second pair was without the top component of the first pair (Ap-1), and all seven components give a load with the same sign (Table 3).

The immune root of the second pair is represented by rod-shaped neutrophils and eosinophils which are subject to the **upregulation** by **Ap-4**, by monocytes and C-reactive protein **downregulated** by **Ap-2** and Lymphocytes in total **upregulated** by **Ap-2**. But the main array is represented by immune parameters that are subject to **suppression** or **activation** by the variations of the magnetic field on other days.

Table 14. Factor Structure Matrix for second Ap/Immune pair of Canonical Roots

Left set	Root 2
Ap-6, nT	0,745
Ap-7, nT	0,654
Ap-3, nT	0,483
Ap-5, nT	0,440
Ap-0, nT	0,328
Ap-2, nT	0,227
Ap-4, nT	0,311
Right set	Root 2
Immunoglobulins A, g/L	-0,603
CD3 ⁺ CD4 ⁺ T-helper Lymphocytes, %	-0,484
CD3 ⁺ T-active Lymphocytes, %	-0,289
CD22 ⁺ B-Lymphocytes, %	-0,255
Phagocytosis Index vs E. coli, %	-0,242
Entropy of Immunocytogram	-0,208
Interleukin-1, ng/L	-0,156
Monocytes, %	-0,226
C-Reactive Protein, mg/L	-0,058
Lymphocytes in total, %	0,216
Microbial Count for Staph. aureus, Bac/Phagocyte	0,520

Killing Index vs E. coli, %	0,515
CD4 ⁺ CD25 ⁺ T-regulatory Lymphocytes, %	0,381
0-Lymphocytes, %	0,357
Phagocytosis Index vs Staph. aureus, %	0,270
Bactericidal Capacity vs Staph. aureus, 10 ⁹ Bac/L	0,262
Bactericidal Capacity vs E. coli, 10 ⁹ Bacteria/L	0,172
Rod-shaped Neutrophils, %	0,180
Eosinophils, %	0,148

Taken together, the variations of the magnetic field determine this constellation of immune parameters by 74% (Fig. 3).

$R=0,862$; $R^2=0,743$; $\chi^2_{(168)}=255$; $p<10^{-4}$; Λ Prime=0,0187

Fig. 9. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between Ap Geomagnetic indices before 7 days and on day blood sampling (X-line) and Immune parameters (Y-line). Second pair of Roots

Fig. 10. Patterns of coefficients of multiple correlation R between Ap-Indices and acupuncture points and neuro-endocrine-immune complex parameters

Table 15. Factor Structure Matrix for first pair of Canonical Roots of EEG and Immune parameters

Left set	R1
<i>PSD T6-δ, μV²/Hz</i>	-0,372
<i>PSD P4-β, %</i>	-0,335
<i>PSD T6-θ, μV²/Hz</i>	-0,286
<i>PSD T3-δ, %</i>	-0,279
<i>PSD F8-δ, μV²/Hz</i>	-0,269
<i>PSD F7-δ, %</i>	-0,220
<i>PSD F7-β, μV²/Hz</i>	-0,190
<i>PSD F8-θ, μV²/Hz</i>	-0,165
<i>PSD O2-θ, %</i>	0,254
<i>PSD T3-β, %</i>	0,220
<i>PSD F4-θ, %</i>	0,150
Right set	R1
Entropy of Immunocytogram	0,549
CD22 ⁺ B-Lymphocytes, %	0,532
Killing Index vs E. coli, %	0,329
Microbial Count for Staph. aureus, Bacter/Phag	0,303
Immunoglobulins M, g/L	0,269
CD4 ⁺ CD25 ⁺ T-regulatory Lymphocytes, %	0,247
Phagocytosis Index vs Staph. aureus, %	0,181
Bactericidal Capacity vs Staph. aureus, 10 ⁹ B/L	0,137
0-Lymphocytes, %	-0,524
Phagocytosis Index vs E. coli, %	-0,441

$R=0,944$; $R^2=0,892$; $\chi^2_{(624)}=794$; $p<10^{-5}$; $\Lambda \text{ Prime}<10^{-6}$

Fig. 11. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between EEG (X-line) and Immunity (Y-line) parameters. First pair of Roots

Table 16. Factor Structure Matrix for second pair of Canonical Roots of EEG and Immune parameters

Left set	R2
PSD C4- θ , %	0,247
PSD T3- θ , %	0,247
PSD F3- β , %	0,247
PSD F7- β , %	0,239
PSD Fp1- θ , %	0,234
PSD C3- θ , %	0,225
PSD T6- β , %	0,224
PSD F7- θ , %	0,220
PSD T6- θ , %	0,216
PSD T4- β , %	0,215
PSD F8- θ , %	0,196
PSD F4- θ , %	0,185
PSD T6- δ , $\mu V^2/Hz$	0,145
PSD T3- β , %	0,127
PSD T5- δ , %	-0,221
PSD F7- δ , %	-0,203
PSD T3- δ , %	-0,163
Right set	R2
Immunoglobulins A, g/L	0,383
Killing Index vs E. coli, %	0,340
CD4 ⁺ CD25 ⁺ T-regulatory Lymphocytes, %	0,224
Bactericidal Capacity vs E. coli, 10 ⁹ Bacteria/L	0,191
Immunoglobulins M, g/L	0,185

$R=0,908$; $R^2=0,824$; $\chi^2_{(570)}=676$; $p=0,002$; $\Lambda \text{ Prime}<10^{-5}$

Fig. 12. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between EEG (X-line) and Immunity (Y-line) parameters. Second pair of Roots

we consider it necessary to return to the KJ Tracey's [32] scheme of immunological homunculus (Fig. 9) by which the neural structures that are projected onto definite loci responsible for certain immune functions, that is the immune compartment cytokines release

(F3 and/or F4), activation of memory B cells (Fp1 and/or Fp2), dendritic cells maturation (T3 and/T4), regulation of T cells (T5 and/or T6), clonal expansion (P3 and/or P4) and late cytokine release (P? or O?).

Fig. 13. KJ Tracey’s scheme of Immunological Homunculus [32]

The data presented in Table 5 give us reason to bring to court colleagues, first and foremost from the Tracey’s laboratory, our variant of immunological homunculus (Table 7), which contains not only EEG loci to which nerve structures are projected, but also the nature of the rhythm they generate.

Table 17. Factor Structure Matrix for Canonical Roots of HRV&Hormonal and Immune parameters

Left set	R1
Testosterone standardized by sex&age, Z-score	0,426
Vegetative Balance Index, units	0,255
Amplitude of Mode as Sympathetic tone, %	0,199
Cortisol, nM/L	0,059
Mode, msec	-0,766
ULF, %	-0,319
MxDMn as Vagal tone, msec	-0,281
Triangular Index as Vagal tone, units	-0,276
ULF, msec ²	-0,201
SDNN as Vagal tone, msec	-0,166

Triiodothyronine, nM/L	-0,122
Testosterone actual, nM/L	-0,095
Right set	R1
Killing Index vs Staph. aureus, %	0,527
Microbial Count for E. coli, Bacteria/Phagocyte	0,403
Phagocytosis Index vs E. coli, %	0,375
Bactericidal Capacity vs Staph. aureus, 10 ⁹ B/L	0,372
0-Lymphocytes, %	0,323
Bactericidal Capacity vs E. coli, 10 ⁹ Bacteria/L	0,172
Phagocytosis Index vs Staph. aureus, %	0,148
CD22 ⁺ B-Lymphocytes, %	-0,236
CD3 ⁺ CD4 ⁺ T-helper Lymphocytes	-0,217
Killing Index vs E. coli, %	-0,206

R=0,714; R²=0,510; $\chi^2_{(140)}=164$; p=0,049; Λ Prime=0,090

Fig. 14. Scatterplot of canonical correlation between HRV&Hormonal (X-line) and Immunity (Y-line) parameters

It was shown that human brain contains magnetites [9Kirschvink JL et al, 1992] and it was proposed that observed increases in stress hormones, heart rate, and the amount of myocardial infarctions during geomagnetic storms may induced by causing an adaptive stress reaction through the effect of geomagnetic disturbances on brain magnetosomes [10Kirschvink JL et al, 1992a; 11Breus TK et al, 2008].

There are evidences that adaptive immune system can be affected by very low magnetic field. Magnetic field as low as geomagnetic field can significantly change lymphocyte Ca²⁺ uptake [16Walleczek J, 1992]. In addition, through three proposed mechanisms, geomagnetic field can change leukocyte behavior, activation and adhesion by inducing the membrane-mediated signal transduction cascades, like the time that a ligand-receptor interaction activates the cell [16,17Jandova A et al, 2005; 18Simko M et al, 2004; 19Cocek A et al, 2008]. Those mechanisms include changes of ion flux, especially Ca²⁺ across cell membrane, cyclotron resonance and dissociation of protein-ion complex by changing quantum states of ions in their structures in the membrane proteins [17Jandova A et al, 2005]. There are also

evidences that magnetic fields can enhance release of reactive oxygen species by T cells and macrophages [18Simko M et al, 2004].

On the PubMed and PMC resources we found only works on the *long-term* immunotropic effects of the *artificial* magnetic field [27Bonhomme-Faivre L et al, 2003; 28Frahm J et al, 2006; 29Lupke M et al, 2006], which makes it impossible to compare their data with ours.

Therefore, we are pleased to consider YuP Gorgo's et al [30/2018] recent study. The monitoring of specific intensity of bacteria *Photobacterium phosphoreum* luminescence has been carried out for 2 months (September-October 2015) and it was compared to the daily values of activity of the geomagnetic field in the conditions of Kyiv, during the research of bioluminescence. Variation determination of the geomagnetic field was conducted from data of Space Environment Center, NOAA&U.S. Air Force. The inverse proportional reliable average correlation was defined between the values of specific bacterial luminescence and the K-p ($r=-0,41$) as well as A-p ($r=-0,41$) indexes of the geomagnetic field, and with the values of flux of Sun radiation at a wavelength 10,7 cm - reliable directly proportional correlation ($r=0,305$). Interestingly, the average values of Ap-indexes were close to those in our observations (in September $13,7\pm 2,68$ nT; in October $14,9\pm 1,90$ nT). Surprising is the proximity of the force of influence of the intensity of variations of the magnetic field on the day of testing (Ap0) both on the manifestation of bacterial activity and phagocytic function of neutrophils (Table 1). This, in our opinion, confirms the **direct** effect of the geomagnetic field on human neutrophils. The decrease in the level of T-helpers ($r=-0,27$) and B-lymphocytes ($r=-0,19$) reflects, in our opinion, the weakening of their expression of CD4 and CD22 receptors, respectively, as evidenced by the positive correlation of the Ap-index with the level of 0-lymphocytes ($r=0,26$).

It was proposed that membrane-mediated Ca^{2+} signaling processes are involved in the mediation of the electromagnetic field effects on the immune system [16Walleczek J, 1992]. Application of low frequency electromagnetic fields produce parallel shifts in Ca^{2+} uptake and DNA replication intensity in stimulated lymphocytes [31Conti P et al, 1985]. Exposure of immune cells to static magnetic field resulted in **decrease of phagocytic activity**, inhibition of mitogenic response to Con A in lymphocytes and enhancement of apoptosis in thymic cells [32Flipo D et al, 1998]. Together, the data demonstrate the possibility of Ca^{2+} signaling-mediated immunomodulating effects of exposure to magnetic fields.

V Zaporozhan and A Ponomarenko [35/2010] propose that proteins of the Cryptochrome family (CRY) are “epigenetic sensors” of the magnetic field fluctuations, i.e., magnetic field-sensitive part of the epigenetic controlling mechanism. It was shown that CRY represses activity of the major circadian transcriptional complex CLOCK/BMAL1. At the same time, function of CRY, is apparently highly responsive to weak magnetic field because of radical pairs that periodically arise in the functionally active site of CRY and mediate the radical pair mechanism of magnetoreception. It is known that the circadian complex influences function of every organ and tissue, including modulation of both NF- κ B- and glucocorticoids-dependent signaling pathways. Thus, magnetic fields and solar cycles-dependent geomagnetic field fluctuations are capable of altering expression of genes related to function of NF- κ B, hormones and other biological regulators.

In addition, the effect of geomagnetism on immunocytes through the nervous and endocrine systems seems quite real. Evidence of this was obtained by us on the same contingent and will be reflected in the next article, already prepared for publication.

Solar-induced fluctuations in the ambient geomagnetic field have been correlated with a wide range of biological effects [Muehsam D and Ventura C, 2014], including changes in

ultrastructure of cardiomyocytes, temporal changes in blood pressure [Breus TK et al, 2002], changes in power in the gamma (>30 Hz) and theta (4–8 Hz) brain wave frequencies in humans [Babayev ES and Allahverdiyeva AA, 2007; Mulligan BP et al, 2010], coherence of human EEG oscillations [Novik OB and Smirnov FA, 2013]. Importantly, changes in solar/geomagnetic activity have also been shown to impact human health in a clinically-relevant manner. Increased solar activity has been correlated with a substantially increased rate of myocardial infarctions [Halberg F et al, 2000; Vencloviene J et al, 2013], decreased survival of acute coronary syndromes [Vencloviene J et al, 2014], higher mortality from acute myocardial infarction, higher diastolic arterial pressure in healthy subjects and in treated hypertensive patients, higher prolactin and 17-corticosteroid levels in the peripheral blood, more severe migraine attacks and more admissions for cerebrovascular accident and cerebrovascular insufficiency in male patients, changes in many blood coagulation cellular gradients (platelet count, basophils in the peripheral blood), a rise in platelet aggregation, fibrinogen level and a drop in leukocyte adhesiveness [Stoupel E, 2002], increased mortality due to a wide range of factors [Stoupel E et al, 2002], decreased human lifespan [Lowell WE, Davis GE, Jr, 2008], and increased rate of clinical admissions for convulsive seizures [Rajaram M and Mitra S, 1981]. These results show that in addition to diurnal and seasonal solar rhythms, biological coupling with transient solar storm activity and the 11-year solar cycle also occurs, with clinically and socially significant effects.

Baevsky RM et al [1997] examined how heart rate variability (HRV) relates to the risk of ischemic heart disease (IHD) and may provide a means to assess effects of exposure to geomagnetic storms. In Stockholm, the 24-hour SD of hourly estimates of heart rate (HR) were obtained by Holter monitoring from 50 men who had an acute myocardial infarction or had angina pectoris and compared to that of 50 clinically healthy men of similar age. In Tokyo, the HR 121 normotensives and 176 treated hypertensives was monitored. The incidence of IHD was recorded prospectively for 6 years. These results are aligned with those of a retrospective analysis of archived data on all crews of the Soyuz spacecraft for 1990-1994 focused on ECG from cosmonauts (47 males and 2 females) at times corresponding to geomagnetic storms. The results clearly indicate a decrease in HRV in association with IHD (20,5%, $p=0,002$ in Stockholm, 20,0%, $p=0,04$ in Tokyo). By comparison, the about 30% decrease ($p=0,041$) in RMSSD of HR in cosmonauts studied during a geomagnetic storm as compared to cosmonauts monitored on quiet days adds supportive evidence to the proposition that exposure to geomagnetic disturbances increases cardiovascular disease risk.

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ACCORDANCE TO ETHICS STANDARDS

Tests in patients are conducted in accordance with positions of Helsinki Declaration 1975, revised and complemented in 2002, and directive of National Committee on ethics of scientific researches. During realization of tests from all participants the informed consent is got and used all measures for providing of anonymity of participants.

For all authors any conflict of interests is absent.

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ВЗАЄМОЗВ'ЯЗКИ МІЖ ГЕОМАГНІТНИМ АР-ІНДЕКСОМ ТА ПАРАМЕТРАМИ НЕЙРОЕНДОКРИННО-ІМУННОГО КОМПЛЕКСУ У ПАЦІЄНТІВ З ЙОГО ДИСФУНКЦІЄЮ

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Передумова. Ще в 1990 році Ю. П. Лиманський висунув гіпотезу про акупунктурні точки як полімодальні рецептори системи екоцептивної чутливості. У процесі розвитку гіпотези у 2003 р. було обґрунтовано існування окремої функціональної системи регуляції електромагнітного балансу організму та сформульована робоча концепція світлолікування. В руслі даної гіпотези ми поставили перед собою мету проаналізувати зв'язки між збуреннями геомагнітного поля (за Ар-індексом) і електропровідністю низки точок акупунктури (ТА), з одного боку, і параметрами нейро-ендокринно-імуного комплексу у пацієнтів з його дисфункцією - з іншого

боку. **Матеріал і методи.** Об'єктом спостереження стали 21 чоловік (24-63 р.) та 20 жінок (30-72 р.) з дисфункцією нейроендокринно-імунного комплексу. Кожного пацієнта обстежували двічі з інтервалом у 4 дні. Спостереження проводилися 09.06. та 13.06. 2015, 14.09 та 18.09. 2015, 27-28.03. та 04-05.04. 2018, 28.01. та 01.02. 2019. Ретроспективно реєстрували геомагнітний Ap-індекс в день тестування та протягом попередніх 7 днів, використовуючи ресурс <https://www.spaceweatherlive.com/>. Реєстрували електропровідність 9 пар ТА, параметри електроенцефалограми (ЕЕГ) і варіабельності ритму серця (ВРС), визначали концентрацію в плазмі кортизолу, трийодтироніну і тестостерону, вміст в крові субпопуляцій лімфоцитів, що експресують рецептори CD3, CD4, CD25, CD8, CD22 та CD56, а також сироваткову концентрацію циркулюючих імунних комплексів, імуноглобулінів класів М, G, А, С-реактивного білка та IL-1 β і IL-6. Стан фагоцитарної функції нейтрофілів оцінений за мікробним числом та індексами активності фагоцитозу і кілінгу *Staphylococcus aureus* і *Escherichia coli*. **Результати.** Протягом тижня середній рівень Ap-індексу коливався від 7 до 13 нТл. Максимальні коефіцієнти множинної кореляції з параметрами ТА виявлені для Ap-індексу в день тестування ($R=0,487$), з параметрами ЕЕГ - напередодні реєстрації ($R=0,708$) та за 6 днів до неї ($R=0,685$), з параметрами імунітету - напередодні забору крові ($R=0,768$) і за 5 днів до нього ($R=0,758$), з показниками ВРС і гормонів - за 2 ($R=0,506$) та 7 ($R=0,403$) днів до дослідження. Канонічна кореляція між Ap-індексами за 7 днів до та в день тестування і параметрами ТА становить 0,624, ЕЕГ - 0,886, ВРС і гормонів - 0,766, параметрами імунітету - 0,921. Своєю чергою, параметри імунітету тісно пов'язані з параметрами ЕЕГ ($R=0,944$) та ВРС і гормонів ($R=0,714$). **Висновок.** Збурення геомагнітного поля (Ap-індекс) чинить значний негайний модулюючий вплив на параметри нейроендокринно-імунного комплексу, мабуть, через посередництво точок акупунктури.

Ключові слова: геомагнітний Ap-індекс, точки акупунктури, нейро-ендокринно-імунний комплекс, кореляції, люди.

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